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RURAL TOURISM ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A MECHANISM FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY ON ANEGUNDI, KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This research paper aims to enhance an understanding on the significance of entrepreneurship in rural tourism, which can contribute to sustainable rural development of Anegundi. The study aims to detect and evaluate various obstacles and challenges for tourism entrepreneurial development in the village by identifying existing tourism entrepreneurial culture and climate in Anegundi. It also aims to determine applicable and feasible solutions to deal with issues and huddles in enforcement of rural tourism base entrepreneurship development in Anegundi.

Methodology / Research Approach: According to the purpose of research paper, the *exploratory research approach* has been adopted to conduct the study based on extensive *secondary data* collected from various books, newspapers, websites, articles etc. The aim is to gain familiarity with the entrepreneurial issues, and to acquire a deeper understanding on tourism entrepreneurship.

Findings- Rural tourism entrepreneurship is a crucial mechanism to bring rural development. Rural tourism is capable of generating alternative entrepreneurial opportunities for rural community in order to bring out rural empowerment in the village Anegundi.

Limitations: This research article is purely based on secondary data collection method since it is a conceptual research work. The primary data collection method is not been used to undergo the study.

Practical Implication: The research study reveals that the rural tourism entrepreneurship is an effective mechanism for rural development, as it opens up alternative occupational prospects for the local community of rural area other than agriculture as an occupation.

Originality / Value: The research paper is based on a case study on Anegundi village located in northern Karnataka at koppal district of gangavati taluk and it also reviews various literatures concerning the significance of rural tourism entrepreneurship as a device to bring rural empowerment.

Key words: rural tourism, tourism entrepreneurship, economic growth, rural empowerment, rural development

1. INTRODUCTION

At the present scenario of 21st century Tourism Industry has been identified as a premier smokeless and fast-growing industry in the world with enormous scopes of employment prospects and economic prosperity. The International trade and commerce is significantly influenced by the diverse tourism activities across the globe as its share of contribution is about 9.2 percent in the global GDP. The year 2015 witnessed 1.2 billion of tourist arrivals indicating an increase of 4.4 percent of International tourist arrivals as compared to the year 2012 which witnessed one billion of tourist inflow worldwide. The UNWTO Index also indicates an enhancement of international tourist arrivals by 4% worldwide in 2016.

The trends observed in the tourism industry in recent years indicate increased demand for nature base tourism and rural tourism. Good management of rural tourism can make a positive contribution in supporting the rural economy and community and become one of the main forces influencing the direction of regional development. However, to achieve a regions true potential, care needs to be taken to conserve the rural heritage, biodiversity, landscapes and local culture.

India as a sub-Continent witnesses its sixty seven percent of population residing in rural areas and sub urban areas as per the historic data chart published by World Bank in 2014. The decline of agriculture as a primary occupation is identified as one of major drawback and economic crises in the rural areas. The rise of unemployment and poverty among the rural Indian are the key challenges which prevails in nation's economic system. In this scenario the Tourism Entrepreneurship can be recognized as suitable mechanism to bring out enormous scopes of employment opportunities, economic prosperity among the rural Indian. Rural tourism has emerged as an alternative occupation prospect in India which may contribute to rural economic empowerment of the nation

Rural development is increasingly associated with entrepreneurship, which is considered as a central force of economic growth and development. What is needed is an environment enabling entrepreneurship in rural areas. Entrepreneurial orientation to rural development is based on stimulating local entrepreneurs, thus creating jobs and adding economic value to a region and community and at the same time keeping scarce resources within the community. Tourism's role in rural development is fundamentally an economic one and can help to sustain and improve the quality of life in rural areas. Tourism comprises mostly small enterprises and the role of tourism entrepreneurs can be important for the development of rural tourism. The question of how sustainable tourism development may be integrated into the sustainable rural development is important to the success of businesses, regions and communities in which they operate.

Rural Tourism Entrepreneurship is aiming to provide various entrepreneurial opportunities in the form of various small scale industries catering to tourists' needs and requirements which unwraps up numerous job prospects for the local community of the rural setting. The research study seeks to identify various entrepreneurial opportunities available in one of the rural setting of India among numerous rural areas, located in Northern part of Karnataka state at Koppal district in Gangavatti Taluk named as 'Anegundi' .

Rural tourism entrepreneurship in Anegundi also contributes in revitalization of rural culture of local community in the rural setting depicting performing art forms, fairs and rural festivals, rural cuisine, way of living in country side of rural Karnataka and rural handicrafts to the tourist community at a national and international level.

2. THE OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This research paper aims to enhance an understanding of the significance of entrepreneurship in rural tourism and to identify ways of enhancing entrepreneurship in tourism, which can contribute to sustainable rural development of Anegundi. The study aims to identify rural tourism entrepreneurship as an important mechanism for rural development of Anegundi as well as a valuable instrument for revitalization of local rural culture of the village.

The specific key areas of the objectives of the research paper are;

- 1) To identify the current tourism entrepreneurial culture and climate of Anegundi

- 2) To detect and evaluate various obstacles and challenges for tourism entrepreneurial development in Anegundi
- 3) To determine applicable and feasible solutions to deal with issues and huddles in enforcement of rural tourism base entrepreneurship development in Anegundi

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

3.1 Introduction

The concept of entrepreneurship has a long and rich tradition within economic system. The root of the word ‘entrepreneur’ can be traced 800 years back to the French verb ‘entreprendre’, which means ‘to undertake’. Despite the number of published literature that might be related to the theory of entrepreneurship, no generally accepted theory has emerged. The concept of ‘entrepreneur’ in the economic system was first acknowledged by an economist Richard Cantillon (1680–1734). He formally defines the entrepreneur as ‘the agent who buys means of production at certain prices in order to combine them into a new product.’ is uncertainty. By engaging in arbitrage and bearing risk, the entrepreneur has an equilibrating function within the economic system.

Conducting a literature review is significant in research study to gain familiarity with the concept and theory of Tourism entrepreneurship development in rural areas which would help in conducting the study and interpreting the findings and recommendations. The literature studies that have been conducted reveal the impact of tourism entrepreneurial activities in rural areas of India and abroad. During the literature review, it is noticed that the term “tourism entrepreneurship” has a significant role to play in bringing rural empowerment which can be viewed in the following.

3.1.1 Maia Lordkipanidze (2002), Enhancing Entrepreneurship in Rural Tourism for Sustainable Regional Development.

The eminent research scholar interprets about the significance of entrepreneurship in rural tourism and to identify the ways of enhancing entrepreneurship in tourism, which can contribute to the sustainable regional development. The Söderslätt region, Sweden, is selected as a case study since it is one of the most agriculture intensive parts of Sweden and problems such as a decline in agriculture and outward migration of local people are observed. There is

interest and willingness expressed by representatives from local municipalities to develop the region in a sustainable way through Rural Tourism Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (RTEDP).

3.1.2 Mamta Mantri, “Three Stones Make A Hearth: A Theoretical Model For Rural Skill Development And Capacity Building At Anegundi, Hampi World Heritage Site”

The author Mamta Mantri briefly states about the study area (Anegundi) and reveals the facts concerning the capacity building of local community at Anegundi village through various skill developmental programs initiated by The Kishkindha Trust, a non-governmental organization in association with various affiliated specialized agencies. The author also strongly advocates the role of ‘*Rule Tourism*’ in Anegundi creating scopes of Tourism Entrepreneurship in bringing economic empowerment in Anegundi.

3.1.3 Carmelia SURUGIU, “Development of Rural Tourism through Entrepreneurship “

The research scholar briefly describes about Romanian rural tourism entrepreneurship and the developer’s efforts to bring out rural empowerment in Romanian village through rural tourism is very much evident in the following statement:

“the issues of entrepreneurship in rural tourism, identifying its potential to stimulate the rural areas of Romania. Tourism in general and rural tourism in particular are dominated by small scale business where the spirits of initiative, desire to achieve and the ability to identify market opportunities fructify effectively are essential. The Romanian entrepreneurship began to revive after 1989, the efforts initially being shy and the researches carried out indicate that Romanian developer in rural tourism is still optimistic and open to accumulate new knowledge and is interested to develop a business. “

3.2 Identification of the Research Gap

The review of literature on tourism entrepreneurship development reveals that the phenomenon of entrepreneurial activities has attracted the interest and research attention of a broad range of management disciplines. Rural tourism Entrepreneurship became a vehicle to solve regional and national problems and to stimulate economic growth .This research study on rural tourism entrepreneurship development reveals that tourism entrepreneurial activities in rural sector and its development as a tool for solving the problem of poverty. Self-employment, enhancement in better livelihood and economy growth has encouraged the rural

population to venture into rural tourism base entrepreneurship. The literature deals extensively on economic growth through rural tourism entrepreneurship with local community participation and support of non-governmental organizations, affiliated agencies as well as the local government. This research paper is an attempt to study the significance of rural tourism as a mechanism for entrepreneurship development especially in Anegundi Villages of koppal District, Karnataka, India. The study aims at specifying scopes of rural tourism entrepreneurship and role of institutions in supporting the tourism entrepreneurial development in rural area.

3.3 SUMMARY

The literature review has revealed that the entrepreneurship development has been a source of economic growth, rural development, job opportunity and business enhancement and provides a source of livelihood for villagers under poverty line. In Anegundi, Karnataka, the rural tourism entrepreneurship development has been on rise since the introduction of The Kishkindha Trust (1997), which has encouraged many capacity building skill development programs to enhance self-driven economic independency among rural people through entrepreneurship development. The literature made available by various researchers has given the investigator the scope of understanding entrepreneurship development and its effectiveness. One of the highlights was the initiatives of NGOs and local governing bodies to train local community which is an important aspect of fostering rural entrepreneurs. Several researchers have concluded that training has built-up the entrepreneurial culture and also enabled the growth of an individual. Generally, the under- developed countries have taken up entrepreneurship as a tool to eliminate poverty and to provide poor people a source of income. As per our literature review countries like Sweden, Romania has been prominently exposing entrepreneurial development in rural areas through rural tourism. India has also been promoting entrepreneurship in rural sector through rural tourism to make it on a par with developed Nations.

4. METHODOLOGY

The methodology is applied to conduct the study chosen in order to acquire information and deduce conclusions about significance of tourism entrepreneurship to promote rural development in Anegundi, situated in Northern part of Karnataka at koppal district in order to achieve rural economic empowerment.

According to the purpose of this study, the exploratory research approach has been adopted to conduct the study. The aim is to gain familiarity with the entrepreneurial issues, and to gain a deeper understanding about the tourism entrepreneurship as an effective mechanism for rural development through successful local community participation.

In order to collect the data the secondary source of data collection method is adopted extensively to get an insight on rural setting of Anegundi. The secondary data on Anegundi contribute toward the formation of background information, needed in order to undergo detailed study on Anegundi to detect and evaluate various obstacles and opportunities for tourism entrepreneurial development in Anegundi.

5. THE STUDY AREA

The rural setting of Anegundi is the study area, a small village in a Koppal District of Gangavathi taluk in Karnataka. Its name (Anegundi) is a combination of two words. ‘Ane’ in Kannada means an Elephant. ‘Gundi’ means a ‘pit’. Thus ‘Anegundi’ would mean elephants’ pit. It was so called because it was meant for bathing of royal elephants of Vijayanagara Empire. Anegundi was the capital of Vijayanagar Empire and later on it shifted to Hampi, It is located 356.8 kilometers from capital city of Karnataka. Anegundi falls in the core zone of the World Heritage Site of Hampi known for its unique sculptures and architecture style of vernacular rural houses, distinctive Anegundi Utsav, rural handicrafts, folklore and rural natural beauty makes it more precious and attractive rural tourist destination.

6. THE GENERAL FRAMEWORK OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ANEGUNDI

With the advent of new economic policy adopted in India since 1991, the contribution of agriculture in national income has declined to 26 percent and that of service sector has increased to more than half of the total national income. Therefore, service sector emerged as a driving force for economic growth in India. Due to which agriculture as an occupation became an ignorant economic activity and got insignificant support from the government authorities.

Agriculture being the primary occupation in the rural setting of Anegundi at koppal district of Gangavati Taluk situated in Northern part of Karnataka, was not sufficient to bring out economic empowerment and development, as entrepreneurship development in the field of agriculture has failed drastically due of lack of support from the government authorities . The

local governing authorities failed to cope up with challenges thrown various external business environmental forces.

The lack of modern technical skill, shortage of economic resources, education, awareness and lack of interest were various obstacles and challenges which the government and the local community failed to address. The seasonal nature of agriculture and lack of irrigation facilities creates problem of seasonal and cyclical unemployment. Large numbers of persons employed in agriculture are of disguised nature. They seem to be employed but their marginal productivity is zero. Disguised nature of agriculture forced the people to migrate from rural to urban areas creating pressure on cities in terms of additional facilities for housing, sanitation, water and also employment. The situation of an uneducated, unskilled rural labour migrating from rural to urban areas is like second class citizens without their own identity.

6.1 Emergence of Tourism entrepreneurship in Anegundi

Rural tourism entrepreneurship as an alternative occupation prospect in rural setting of Anegundi was introduced by The Kishkindha Trust (TKT), a nongovernmental organisation led by Ms Shama Pawar (niece of Shri Sharad Pawar) in the year 1997, with a mission to see the local community of Anegundi achieve social, economic empowerment through conservation of natural and architectural heritage, and doing so secure the future of site through sustainable integration of the people of the land through rural tourism entrepreneurship.

TKT initiated in developing an integrated systems for sustainable livelihoods, architectural conservation, crafts, and education through performing arts, etc., in the village of Anegundi- a part of Hampi World Heritage Site by working with grassroots communities. In a population of about 20,000 in the village, TKT has touched a thousand lives through its many tourism entrepreneurship developmental programs such as introduction of eighty Self Help Groups (SHGs) known as '*Bhoomi Society for working women*' to achieve the goal of rural women entrepreneurship, facilitating development of homestay arrangement, establishment of multi cuisine restaurants by locals, patronising local folk artists and performers, introducing village guides and volunteers to guide tourists by inducing rural tourism as livelihood strategy and introducing the concept of community participation in catering tourism services to the tourist community in Anegundi.

These thousand men, women and youth of Anegundi reflects a deeper sense of commitment to the values of community living and betterment, empathy towards heritage and conservation, and the historical significance of the space that they inhabit, along with meaningful and healthy means of living. As an intent to spread out the benefits of these sporadic activities in an even and deliberate fashion, so that the locals of the village-the real stakeholders, earn their livelihoods while remaining connected to their homeland and culture, It built a comprehensive program for capacity building of the village to introduce various entrepreneurial opportunities in the core areas of Hospitality sector, Crafts and Design, Tourism and Heritage Management and Entrepreneurship, Tourism Management in Anegundi

TKT does not want to merely to set up Anegundi as a tourist destination but to infuse the vitality of the lost heritage and culture, to create a community oriented atmosphere and quality of life in the locals, which shall be passed on the visitor, domestic and international, thus making it an authentic and rich experience. Capacity building is meant for inculcating the intrinsic importance of the value attached with the village and the site, training that will inculcate knowledge about the historical significance of the place and tools to tap the economic and social potential of their location, and also training them to run their businesses imaginatively and creatively in keeping with international standards.

The EDP strategies also facilitates in building and preservation of local crafts, Architectural Conservation, ensuring training and development of villagers by establishing library and children's centre as well as education centres. It also enabled the existence of various small scale handicraft enterprises exhibiting Banana Fibre Craftsmanship, Organic agriculture and forest based products for daily consumption, shops. Food Courts during religious and cultural events & Catering, Festival of ARTS, River Tern Concerts, Moon light Santhe (Market), etc. are various live examples of rural tourism attractions in Anegundi where rural tourism entrepreneurship development is applicable.

6.1.1 Capacity Building in Entrepreneurship, Administration and Management

TKT in association with government and various affiliated agencies have determined a capacity building framework that need to be achieved in order to establish rural tourism ventures and to empower the villagers through rural tourism.

In order to achieve managerial efficiency, it is important to achieve professionalization of management amongst the community. The stakeholders in the village shall be an integral part of the policy frame and procedural guidelines at the planning stage and in the regulation of the management performance towards achievement of its objectives at the control stage. Their entrepreneurial and managerial efficiency shall be enhanced by incorporating better career management methods and techniques through a process of continuous training and development.

The villagers shall undergo renovation and reconstruction at Anegundi, shall be the symbols of businesses, independence and financial successes. One of the first steps towards making these business incubators a sustained source of income generation and a huge financial success and is to create 'serial innovators and entrepreneurs', who are habitual and compulsive in their passion for innovation and creating substantial new enterprise, through introducing new products, processes, or new service delivery systems. Furthermore, these entrepreneurs shall provide leadership in creating substantial forms of wealth - financial and/or social - from the new opportunities they identify, exploit, and grow into sustainable organizations. Fundamental to the success of initiatives to develop entrepreneurs is a concurrent development of processes for identifying and developing 'entrepreneur enablers'. The ability to enable entrepreneurship is the most critical component in developing the processes of coaching, mentoring, business generation, business incubation, and education to produce the necessary abundance of successful, world-class new ventures.

7. THE CHALLENGES IN TOURISM ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT AT ANEGUNDI

An application of Tourism entrepreneurship Development in the rural setting of Anegundi is challenging despite of its potential socio economic benefits. The nature and the process of implementation of this Tourism entrepreneurial developmental strategy in bringing rural development may greatly affect the success of rural community empowerment. The various issues and challenges of TED strategy to be addressed are as follows:

- **Conflicts between Gram panchayat and The Kishkindha Trust**

To initiate various Tourism entrepreneurial developmental strategy through human resource or youth capacity building available in the village, the most challenging issue was lack of

faith, cooperation and coordination between Gram panchayat of Anegundi village and The Kishkindha Trust. The Gram panchayat as local governing of the village and TKT encountered with various conflicts among the two interest groups, due to lack of confidence of GP on The Kishkindha trust

- **Community mobilization**

The rural community mobilization of the village to implement the EDP plans and various developmental strategies formulated by TKT in association with various affiliated agencies was real challenging as the local community lack in awareness, cooperation & coordination, knowledge concerning rural tourism economic significance and insufficient skill base talented human resource to execute the plan successfully.

- **Lack of Basic Infrastructure**

Deficiency of basic infrastructure facilities such as connectivity to the village through various mode of transportation was insufficient, lack of sufficient power supply, communication facilities and acute shortage of safe drinking water supply in the village was some major issues, which delayed to carry out the developmental plan effectively. The inadequacy of sufficient infrastructural facilities are the major huddles or obstacles in executing entrepreneurial developmental plan , as it deviated and delayed implementation of EDP strategies & plan.

- **Inadequacy of available Resources**

Inadequacy of various economic resources such financial support, talented skilled labours, modern technical equipment to implement any development strategy effectively and efficiently.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

8.1 RECOMMENDATIONS

The possible recommendations to enforce rural tourism entrepreneurship development in Anegundi, some recommendations are proposed based on the issues and challenges as mentioned above.

- **Improving entrepreneurial culture and climate**

In order to create an entrepreneurial culture, the author recommends developing of positive attitude towards entrepreneurship, which is a prerequisite for more locals to set up their

tourism enterprises. As entrepreneurship demands an enabling environment, less bureaucratic interference and more practical support from the local governing bodies has to be provided. Policies to increase the supply of entrepreneurs and policies for increasing demand for entrepreneurship, can significantly improve entrepreneurial climate and speed up entrepreneurial activities. Also, development of entrepreneurial attitudes and culture can be achieved through education and training programs.

- **Educational program for tourism entrepreneurial development in Anegundi**

Development of entrepreneurial culture creates accessibility of entrepreneurial opportunities. However, entrepreneurs in rural areas are often hindered, due to different problems (e.g., they are suffering from lack of necessary motivation to be innovative and lack of relevant education related to the development of their enterprises). More specifically they face problems such as lack of necessary knowledge to plan a new business or tourism project, or raising money for the project. Business plans are an important prerequisite for starting a new enterprise, to transform business ideas into a working operation.

The local Gram panchayat in Anegundi should recognize the importance of rural tourism entrepreneurship, in order to address issues like the decline of agriculture and emigration, and to enhance innovation and creation of new businesses. In order to address above-mentioned issues, educational program targeting specifically rural entrepreneurs can be proposed. The objective of this educational program will be to enhance entrepreneurship in the region by reaching potential entrepreneurs through the delivery of entrepreneurial education and the promotion of an entrepreneurial environment. The gram panchayat in association with educational institutions and TKT could carry out this. Educational programs should involve the economic, social and environmental aspects of sustainable entrepreneurial development. When starting a business, environmental considerations, quality of life and economic benefits are to be achieved. The most important stakeholders benefiting from the educational program will be local entrepreneurs acquiring necessary knowledge and contributing to the sustainability of their region.

The elements of the educational program can be *e-learning for rural entrepreneurs* which can help to address the problems through distance learning courses e.g. courses in sustainability issues, in marketing, management, book keeping, project development, communication, sales, and other subjects. Moreover, study circles can be another element of the program - as a way of bringing potential entrepreneurs together and involving local community in the tourism entrepreneurial development process.

- **Access to financial resources**

In order to create a new business or to expand the existing one, rural entrepreneurs need financial resources to stay competitive and to grow. One of the major difficulties they face is access to finance. Financial support can be provided by venture capital funds, but it is necessary to stimulate the interest of venture capital firms in investing in local enterprises by creating proper business plans. It is also important to provide easy access to the information about different types and sources of financing. Creating financial databases where entrepreneurs can easily find information about how, where, and on which conditions financial help can be provided, can do this.

- **Cooperation and coordination among the interest groups**

In order to overcome the lack of cooperation, networks and collaborative agreements is recommended among the stakeholders, government, various specialized affiliated agencies and TKT. This cooperation may relate to marketing as well as to standards, booking systems, mutual help, training, etc. Also networks can provide support to better understand the tourism business, tourist market's needs and marketing environments in which enterprises operate.

It is also important to promote and expand women's participation in rural tourism entrepreneurship, through better training in basic business skills and improved access to market opportunities in non-traditional sectors, aiding networking and associations of women entrepreneurs, and increasing the visibility of women as role models and mentors.

8.2 Conclusions

Sustainable tourism entrepreneurship development seeks to address the problems associated with the rural development, decline of agriculture and emigration of the rural population. Therefore, it is necessary that the environment is enabling and favorable for entrepreneurial development and for the growth and development of existing enterprises in rural areas. But the biggest challenge today is to find ways to give more regions the option to pursue the path to entrepreneurship development. For policymakers there is a significant challenge in fostering new regions to become more entrepreneurial. Government's basic role is to create new programs to solve problems. However, encouraging entrepreneurial communities cannot be accomplished in the traditional 'top-down' way. The key to a region's entrepreneurial success stems from a 'bottom-up' approach and a regional commitment to entrepreneurial growth. Perhaps government's most effective tool is to stimulate and support private sector institutions as well as various non-governmental organizations like The Kishkindha Trust

(TKT) that work to benefit locals through capacity building of the community and to stimulate regional entrepreneurial development. Even if there are no easy solutions to deal with the issues like unemployment and poverty, it is important that the local governing body i.e. Gram Panchayat closely in association with stakeholders, affiliated specialized agencies and non-governmental organization must seek to develop such self-driven economic independency that are economically, environmentally and socially sustainable.

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